

ADENOID DISEASE IN THE KHOREZM REGION SPECIFICITY

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Relevance of the topic. Currently, the increasing number of patients with adenoid disease among the population of Khorezm and its dependence on environmental conditions remains one of the pressing problems for Khorezm otorhinolaryngologists. This can be seen in the increase in the number of daily visits of patients with adenoids to KTMP, OP and QOP, as well as private clinics. The severity of the problem can be judged by changes in the general condition of patients with adenoids, difficulty breathing through the nose, nasal discharge, decreased work capacity, and drowsiness.

Research materials and methods. A record of patients who applied to the clinic of the Urgench State Medical Institute during 2024 was collected for the study. Posterior and anterior rhinoscopy, lateral radiography, and endoscopy were performed.

Results and analysis. Recently, adenoid disease has become more common in the Khorezm region among young people. The origin of adenoid disease can be linked to several causes. Among them, frequent colds, unsuccessful home treatments, the drying up of the Aral Sea, and the deterioration of the ecological environment due to the rise of dust and various chemical compounds into the air occupy an important place. Many patients in the medical history report that they have been suffering from the disease for several years and have used various vasodilators at home. Patients primarily report difficulty breathing through the nose, runny nose, nasopharyngeal discomfort, snoring, and decreased attention, accompanied by headaches and general malaise. The patients underwent the following therapeutic procedures:

Antihistamines (diazoline, suprastin, cetirizine, desloratadine, loratadine, etc.), antibiotics, vasospasmodic drugs, and 2% protorgol are recommended for grade 1 adenoid disease. Surgical interventions are performed for stages 2-3 of adenoid disease, and it is recommended to engage in sports.

Conclusion: Adenoid disease is a widespread disease among children, and timely diagnosis and treatment are of great importance. Scientific research shows that a conservative approach can be effective at an early stage. However, in cases where the risk of complications is high, surgical intervention is the correct course of action. For the purpose of preventive measures, it is recommended to strengthen immunity, treat infections in a timely manner, and engage in sports.

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